

Basic Git Cheat Sheet - Developer (v1.0.0)

For Newcomers to Software Programming World

Goal

1. Help newcomers contribute to an existing Git repository without already knowing repository maintenance.

Covered Topics

1. Identify Git flow (Upstream)
2. Clone a Git repository
3. Get Git status
4. Switch branch
5. Stage a commit
6. Create a commit
7. Synchronize prior to pushing (rebase)
8. Push local commits to remote branch
9. Release commits / Branch merges
10. Pull updates from remote branch

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Graphics	Description	Command
<p>The diagram illustrates the relationship between a remote repository and a local repository. On the left, under 'Remote', there are two vertical lines representing branches: 'Master' and 'Branch', each with a blue dot at the top. A green cloud-like shape below them is labeled 'Github / Gitlab'. On the right, under 'Local', there are also two vertical lines for 'Master' and 'Branch', each with a blue dot. A green cloud-like shape below them is labeled 'Laptop / PC'. A vertical dashed line separates the Remote and Local sections.</p>	<p>NAME Identify Git flow</p> <p>GOAL Identify remote/local role</p> <p>WHEN When you start work on your laptop / PC. You need to identify where your upstream is pointing to.</p> <p>WHY To know the location your local repository links to. It can be in Github.com / Gitlab.com / local directory (different places).</p>	<pre>\$ cat \$PWD/.git/config # read the "origin" location. ... [remote "origin"] url = git@gitlab.com:ZORALab/bissetii.git fetch = +refs/heads/*:refs/remotes/origin/* ...</pre>
<p>The diagram shows the cloning process. On the left, under 'Remote', there are two vertical lines for 'Master' and 'Branch', each with a blue dot. On the right, under 'Local', there are two empty vertical lines for 'Master' and 'Branch'. A green arrow points from the Remote section to the Local section, indicating the direction of cloning.</p>	<p>NAME Clone a Git repository</p> <p>GOAL Create a local repository based on remote repository.</p> <p>WHEN Local machine does not have a copy of a remote repository.</p>	<pre>\$ git clone <URL> EXAMPLE \$ git clone https://gitlab.com/zoralab/bissetii.git \$ git clone git@gitlab.com:zoralab/bissetii.git</pre>

Graphics	Description	Command
<p>The diagram shows two vertical timelines representing Git branches. On the left, under 'Remote', there are two vertical lines labeled 'Master' and 'Branch', each with a blue dot at the top. On the right, under 'Local', there are also two vertical lines labeled 'Master' and 'Branch', each with a blue dot at the top. A dashed vertical line separates the Remote and Local sections. A green cloud containing '???' is positioned between the local Master and Branch lines, indicating an unknown state or conflict.</p>	<p>NAME Get Git status</p> <p>GOAL To figure out what is going on in a git repository.</p> <p>WHEN When you're unsure about what to do and what is going on.</p> <p>WHY</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To make sure you're not going to mess up on-going development. 2. To get the current status. 3. To get the next instructions in the current development. 	<pre>\$ git status</pre>
<p>The diagram shows two vertical timelines representing Git branches. On the left, under 'Remote', there are two vertical lines labeled 'Master' and 'Branch', each with a blue dot at the top. On the right, under 'Local', there are also two vertical lines labeled 'Master' and 'Branch', each with a blue dot at the top. A dashed vertical line separates the Remote and Local sections. A green cloud containing 'Work here' is positioned between the local Master and Branch lines, indicating active work on a branch.</p>	<p>NAME: Switch branch</p> <p>GOAL To switch to a different branch ("timeline")</p> <p>WHEN When you need to do something on a specific branch like experimentations, checking things out, etc.</p> <p>WHY To ensure certain actions would not mess up one branch's purpose from another. Example:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "master" branch can be used for customer version 2. "staging" is the test version of next customer release 3. "next" branch is the cutting edge development. 	<pre>\$ git checkout <branch name></pre> <p>EXAMPLE</p> <pre>\$ git checkout master \$ git checkout next \$ git checkout staging</pre>

Graphics	Description	Command
	<p>NAME Stage a commit</p> <p>GOAL To stage a new commit.</p> <p>WHEN To freeze time of a particular development without creating a commit (“freeze time point for time travel”).</p> <p>WHY To ensure you develop things in a stable manner. These commits (“the frozen time point”) allows you to travel between them easily.</p> <p>HOW By staging your required changes on files.</p>	<pre># To add file into staging \$ git add <file> # To remove file from the stage \$ git reset <file> EXAMPLE \$ git add src/core.c \$ git reset src/core.obj</pre>
	<p>NAME Create a commit</p> <p>GOAL To create a commit (freeze a time).</p> <p>WHEN When a single development purpose is fulfilled and worthy to be committed as one single commit.</p> <p>WHY To ensure the incremental commitment is worthy.</p>	<pre># Commit with signature \$ git commit -s</pre>

Graphics	Description	Command
	<p>NAME Synchronize prior to p (rebase)</p> <p>GOAL To synchronize with remote branch before pushing your local changes to it.</p> <p>WHEN Before pushing your local changes to remote branch.</p> <p>WHY To ensure the timeline is synchronized with the remote branch before pushing your local changes to it.</p> <p>This can remove unnecessary merge commits caused by your changes.</p>	<pre># Switch to that branch first if # you haven't done so. \$ git checkout <branch> # Pull updates from remote \$ git pull --rebase # solve any conflicts appearing # with your local changes. Always # read your git status carefully for # instructions.</pre>
	<p>NAME Push local commits to remote branch</p> <p>GOAL To ensure the remote branch is synchronized with the local branch.</p> <p>OR To upstream your changes to the remote branch.</p> <p>WHEN When the local branch has commits ahead of the remote branch and the base are the same.</p> <p>WHY To upstream your changes for the benefit of all.</p>	<pre># OPTIONAL - Switch to that # branch first if you haven't # done so. \$ git checkout <branch> # Push it \$ git push</pre>

Graphics	Description	Command
	<p>NAME Release commits / Branch merges</p> <p>GOAL To ensure changes at a remote branch is merged into its different branch.</p> <p>WHEN When the maintainer wants to release a set of commits into a new branch. (Releasing).</p> <p>WHY To make it an official release.</p> <p>HOW 2 ways to do it: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Merge request 2. Local rebase merge. </p> <p>IMPORTANT NOTE For any local rebase merge, any conflicts appeared from rebase command must be resolved with careful instructions.</p>	<pre># FOR GITHUB.COM/GITLAB.COM # Create merge request. # FOR LOCAL MERGE **EXPERT ONLY** # 1. Switch to source branch \$ git checkout <source branch> # 2. Update it to the latest \$ git pull --rebase # 3. Switch to target branch \$ git checkout <target branch> # 4. Update it to the latest \$ git pull --rebase # 5. Rebase from source branch \$ git rebase <source branch> # 6. Push to remote \$ git push</pre>
	<p>NOTE: This is similar to "Synchronize prior to pushing"</p> <p>NAME Pull updates from remote branch</p> <p>GOAL To synchronize one branch from remote to local.</p> <p>WHEN When you want the remote branch to be in your local branch.</p> <p>WHY Pulling the latest updates from the remote branch.</p>	<pre># Switch to that branch first if # you haven't done so. \$ git checkout <branch> # Pull updates from remote \$ git pull</pre>